

DESIGN AND FABRICATION OF A MOTORIZED MULTI-PURPOSE MECHANICAL CUTTING MACHINE

Md. Mainuddin Sagar*¹, Md. Rezwan Alam*², Rafid Faisal*³, Dr. Mihir Ranjan Halder*⁴

*¹Research Scholar, Department Of Mechanical Engineering, Chittagong University Of Engineering & Technology (CUET), Chittagong, Bangladesh.

*²Research Scholar, Department Of Mechanical Engineering, Khulna University Of Engineering & Technology (KUET), Khulna, Bangladesh.

*³Research Scholar, Department Of Electrical And Electronics Engineering, American International University(AIUB), Bangladesh.

*⁴Professor, Department Of Mechanical Engineering, Khulna University Of Engineering & Technology, (KUET) Khulna, Bangladesh.

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ABSTRACT

This paper clarifies the concept of the “Multi-Purpose Mechanical Cutting Machine “mainly carried out for industries which are production-based. The industries are basically meant for the production of useful goods and services at low production cost, machinery cost, and low inventory cost. Different types of manufacturing operations are carried out by separate machines which requires more time and space. So, in this paper, a multi-purpose cutting machine is developed that would be capable of performing different operations like drilling, blade cutting, hacksaw cutting, pressure cutting, buffing, and grinding operations at different working centers simultaneously. This machine executes various operations at the same time with applicable speed which is regulated by AC motor. It is based on the method of crank slider mechanism, power transmission through pulleys with v-belts and bevel gears. In this machine, a belt-pulley system was used for power transmission at different locations from the main shaft. The crank slider mechanism is used for hacksawing and pressure-cutting operations. On the main shaft, power is transmitted by a belt-pulley mechanism to the other shaft. The system is such that one end consists of a drill chuck having a drill bit for drilling operation and one end consists of an abrasive grinding wheel for the purpose of surface finishing & grinding operations. At another end of the two other shafts consist of a cutting tool and a buffing wheel for the purpose of blade cutting and surface finishing process used to shine wood, metal composites, etc. This machine was designed as a cartable one which facilitates us to perform various cutting operations at different working centers simultaneously as it is driven from a single power source. Different types of performance tests were done with various thicknesses of materials such as 12mm, 4mm, and 2mm. This multi-purpose machine can be used in small industries, remote places, and workshops because of having less human effort, low cost, reduction of floor area, less power usage, and time

Keywords: Cutting Machine, Drill Bit.

I. INTRODUCTION

Arnold [1] have created the notion that innovation in the machine tool industry after long re-investment cycles of about 15 years happens incrementally. However, looking at its recent history, the integration of digital controls technology and computers into machine tools have hit the industry in three waves of technology shocks. The impact of this new technology was underestimated by most of the companies. This article gives an overview of the history of the machine tool industry since numerical controls were invented and introduced and analyzes the disruptive character of this new technology on the market. More about 100 interviews were conducted with decision-makers and industry experts who witnessed the development of the industry over the last forty years. The study establishes a connection between radical technological change, industry structure, and competitive environment. It flashes a number of important occurrences and interrelations that have so far gone unnoticed .

Moriwaki [2] recent trends in the machine tool technologies which are surveyed from the viewpoints of high speed and high performance machine tools, combined multifunctional machine tools, ultra-precision machine tools including advanced and intelligent control technologies.

Shahnawaz et al. [3] studied the design, analysis and fabrication of "MULTIPURPOSE MECHANICAL MACHINE". This mechanical machine is designed to perform multi operations specially drilling, cutting and grinding. The machine is designed to perform all the operations at same time with desired speed. There model of the multi operational machine may be used in industries and domestic operation which can perform mechanical operation like drilling, cutting & grinding of a thin metallic as well as wooden model or body. In this study literature review and problem identification is performed .

Sharad Srivastava¹: improving the conceptual model of a machine that could perform various types of operations at the same time and must be economically efficient. In this machine, in reality, the impulse was given to the main shaft, to which the mechanism of the Scotch yoke is connected directly, the mechanism of the Scotch yoke is used for the cutting operation. In the main axis, they use a conical system for power transmission in two positions. The model allows us to perform the operation in different work centers simultaneously, as it receives units from a single power source. The main goal of this paper model is the conservation of electricity (energy supply), the reduction of costs associated with the use of energy, the increase in productivity [4].

Krishnappa R, et al. (2017): This paper presents the concept of Multi-Function Operating Machine mainly carried out for production based industries. Basically, the industries are meant for Production of useful goods and services at low production cost, machinery cost and low inventory cost. They have developed a conceptual model of a machine which would be capable of performing different operation simultaneously, and it should be economically efficient. In this machine they are actually giving drive to the main shaft to which scotch yoke mechanism is directly attached, scotch yoke mechanism is used for sawing operation. They have use bevel gear system on the main shaft for power transmission at two locations. Through bevel gear we will give drive to drilling center and grinding center. Again, the model facilitates us to get the operation performed at different working center simultaneously as it is getting drive from single power source. The fundamental objectives of this model are conservation of electricity (power supply), reduction in cost associated with power usage, increase in productivity, reduced Floor space [5].

S.S. Kulkarni, et al (2018): It presents the idea of Multi-Function Operating Machine mainly carried out for production based industries. Industries are basically meant for Production of useful goods and services at low production cost, machinery cost and low inventory cost. The model facilitates us to get the operation performed at different working center simultaneously as it is getting drive from single power source. Objective of this model are high production rate, decrease in cost, conservation of electricity (power supply), reduced floor space and low time interval [6].

Frankfurt-am Main, (2011): The crisis is over, but selling machinery remains a tough business. Machine tools nowadays have to be veritable "jack of all trades", able to handle all kinds of materials, to manage without any process materials as far as possible, and be capable of adapting to new job profiles with maximized flexibility. Two highly respected experts on machining and forming from Dortmund and Chemnitz report on what's in store for machine tool manufacturers and users [7].

Yashraj V Patil et (2018): This paper deals with fabrication of multi-purpose tooling machine. This machine is based on the mechanism of belt drive with pulleys, bevel gears, and scotch yoke. The different types of machining process in manufacturing industries are carried out by separate machining machine. It needs more space requirement and time with high costs. But the fabrication of multi-purpose tooling machine, which involves five operations in a single machine. The operations are namely drilling, shaping, cutting, buffing and grinding. This paper is a new concept of manufacturing machines to reduce the work time and save the cost. Multi-purpose operation at the same time with required speed can be performed by this machine which is automatic operated by motor running with the help of electric power supply [8].

Pradip R. Bodade² proposed a machine which is able to perform operations such as drilling, grinding, cutting and manufacturing of "MULTIFUNCTION MACHINES". The industries are mainly assured for the production of goods and services useful at low production costs, low inventory costs and low machine costs. The model allows us to perform the operations in different work centers simultaneously, as it receives units from a single

power source. The goal of this model is to get a single machine capable of various operations at low costs, reduction of space and the conservation of electricity (energy supply). This machine can be used in small industries and in domestic operations [9].

II. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Proposed Methodology

Fig 2.1:

2.2 Working Principle

In the paper the power required for the operations i.e. .blade cutting, pressure cutting, hacksawing, drilling, grinding and buffing were achieved from motor by using v- belts, bevel gears and crank slider mechanism. These are the three major principles on which this proposed model generally works. They are:

- (a) Crank Slider mechanism
- (b) Power transmission through gears.
- (c) Power transmission through v belt and pulleys.

(a) Crank-Slider Mechanism

The Crank Slider mechanism is a reciprocating motion mechanism which converts a linear motion of a slider into rotational motion, or vice-versa. The piston or other reciprocating part is directly coupled to a sliding yoke with slot that engages a pin on the reciprocating part. The shape of the motion of the piston is a pure sine wave over time given a constant rotational speed.

The mechanism is composed of three important parts. Here the crank which is the rotating disc, the slider which slides inside the tube and the connecting rod which joins the parts together. As the slider moves to the right the connecting rod and pushes the wheel round for the 180 degrees of wheel rotation .When the slider begins to move back into the tube, the connecting rod pulls the wheel round to complete the rotation. The crank and the connecting rod are connected with a pin. The basic principle of this mechanism is that as the sliders

moves back and forth it pushes the connecting rod link which then transfer the force to the crank link and the crankshaft then exhibit a rotational motion due to the moment applied by the crank.

Fig 2.2(a): Crank Slider Mechanism

(b) Power transmission through gears

Bevel gears are gears where the axes of the two shafts intersect and the tooth-bearing faces of the gears themselves are conically shaped. Bevel gears are most often mounted on shafts that are 90 degrees apart, but can be designed to work at other angles as well. The pitch surface of a gear is the imaginary toothless surface that you would have by averaging out the peaks and valleys of the individual teeth. The pitch surface of an ordinary gear is the shape of a cylinder. The pitch angle of a gear is the angle between the face of the pitch surface and the axis.

Fig 2.2(b): Bevel pinion.

(c) Power transmission through v belt and pulleys

The V-belt is used to transmit energy from one tree to another by means of pulleys. Which rotate at the same speed or at different speeds. V-belt is used for power transmission with the help of motor.

Fig 2.2(c): V-Belt and Pulley

In this paper the transmission of power through the v belt and pulleys were supplied to the drilling, grinding, buffing, cutting (blade cutting, hacksaw cutting, pressure cutting) operations. The transmission of power through the v belt and pulley to the drilling, cutting and grinding. The belts can be used as a source of movement to monitor relative development. The belts are surrounded by pulleys and may have a turn between the pulleys, and the poles must not be parallel.

2.3 Functional Description

In this paper the arrangement had electrical motors, bevel gears, long shaft, scotch yoke mechanism, drilling, grinding, buffing, cutting (blade cutting, pressure cutting), and sawing operations set up. The motor is mounted at the base of the frame. There are three shafts and five pulleys of the machine.

The power was transmitted to the shaft one from the electrical motor driving by electrical current. Pulley 1 was connected with the motor to the shaft one by belt drive for power transmission and was also used to drive the shaft on which the grinding wheel and the cutting blade were mounted. The grinding wheel was attached at the one end of the shaft one and the blade cutting tool was also attached at the other end of the same shaft.

The crank slider mechanism was placed at the one end of the shaft 2 for doing the hacksaw cutting operations. There was a bevel gear arrangement which had been mounted on a drill shaft at the other end of shaft 2 to get drilling operation. A drill bit was attached on the drill shaft. Pulley 3 was used to drive the shaft 2 through power transmission by belt drive.

The buffing tool was attached at one end of the shaft 3 and the crank slider mechanism was placed at the other end of the same shaft. Pulley 4 was used to drive this shaft to perform the buffing and pressure cutting operations. All the operations are carried out by giving electrical current to the motor. It converts electrical energy into mechanical energy. Then the mechanical energy is transferred to the rotating shaft and split into different operations.

Fig 2.3: Block Diagram of Operating Procedure.

2.4 Operation Performed

Drilling Operation: Drilling is a cutting process that uses a drill bit to cut a hole of circular cross-section in solid materials. It helps removing large amounts of metal to create semi-precision round hole or cavity. Drilling allows a person to make holes through boards, metals, and other materials. Used for last removal of stock on preparation for other operations like boring, reaming, or tapping. Drilling machine plays an important role in mechanical workshops. The purpose of this paper work is to get hold of complete information pertaining to drilling machines. A drilling machine comes in many shapes and sizes, from small hand-held power drills to bench mounted and finally floor-mounted models. In figure 2.4 shows the drilling operation that I had constructed in my paper.

Fig 2.4: Drilling Operation

Grinding Operation: Grinding is machining process that is used to remove material from a work piece via a grinding wheel .As the grinding wheel turns, it cuts material off the work piece. Grinding processes remove very small chips in very large numbers by cutting the action of many small individual abrasive grains. Very smooth surfaces can be gained by the use of the proper grinding wheel. In this paper, the grinding operation had been done very preciously. The grinding operation that had been performed in my paper was shown in fig 2.5.

Fig 2.5: Grinding Operation

Blade Cutting Operation: Blade cutting is the process of cutting a work piece with a blade. Saws, scissors, scalpels or knives all fall into the blade category. Blade cutting is used in a variety of industrial and commercial applications such as butchering, paper slitting, mad cutting, medical practices and many more. Carbon steel is, by far the most superior material to fabricate sharp blades but they can also be composed of stainless steel. In this paper the blade cutting operation had been performed to cut different materials.

Fig 2.6: Blade Cutting Operation

Pressure Cutting Operation: The cutting operation which is done through any sliding force or any pressure is known as the pressure cutting operation. In figure 2.7 shows the pressure cutting operation that I had been performed which can cut metal of 1.5mm to 2mm thickness.

Fig 2.7: Pressure Cutting Operation

Hacksaw Cutting Operation: A hacksaw is a fine-toothed saw originally and mainly made for cutting metal. The equivalent saw for cutting wood is usually called a bow saw. Most hacksaws are hand saws with a C-shaped walking frame that holds a blade under tension. Such hacksaws have a handle, usually a pistol grip, with pins for attaching a narrow disposable blade. On hacksaws, as with most frame saws, the blade can be mounted with

the teeth facing toward or away from the handle, resulting in cutting action on either the push or pull stroke by the crank slider mechanism[10]. In this paper, the hacksaw cutting blade had been used to cut different sizes of mild steel arrangement with crank slider mechanism.

Fig 2.8: Hacksaw Cutting Operation

Buffing Operation: Buffing is defined as a finishing process that involves the use of a loose abrasive on a wheel. It produces a bright-luster finish on metal and composites. Buff wheels are impregnated with liquid rouge or a greaseless compound-based matrix of specialized fine abrasive called compound. To polish a work piece, a manufacturing company may use a wheel that is covered with an abrasive disc. In this paper, the buffing operation had been performed for removing superficial material from the surface of a work piece.

Fig 2.9: Buffing Operation

III. MODELING AND ANALYSIS

3.1 Design Consideration

While designing the proposed multi-purpose mechanical cutting machine, some factors were considered. The considerations were made from the general perspective and mechanical perspective. So, considerations were categorized into two sections. First one is General Considerations and the second one is Mechanical Considerations. These two types of considerations are described below,

a) General Considerations: The general considerations were,

- Simple design and construction are required.
- The assemble and disassemble process should be easy.
- Operating system should be easy.
- Maintenance process should be simple.
- The cost of the construction should be low.

b) Mechanical Consideration: The mechanical considerations were,

- The main construction should be light and able to bear forces.
- The parts should be replaceable.
- The motor should be replaceable and can be disassembled for repairing.
- The force on the frame should be uniformly distributed.

- The shaft should be rigid enough to withstand the load.

3.2 Proposed CAD model

Keeping in mind the general and mechanical considerations, the CAD model of the Multi-Purpose Mechanical Cutting Machine was done in SOLIDWORKS 2020. Fig. 3.2(a) shows the CAD model of the machine.

Fig 3.2(a): CAD Model of the Paper (Designed)

3.3 Selection of Materials

In this paper, the frame, shaft, the crank was made by using mild steel. Mild steel is a ductile metal that can be quickly welded. Mild steel has the same Young's Modulus of tension and compression ($2.0-2.1 \times 10^5 \text{ N/mm}^2$). Concrete and mild steel have almost identical coefficients of thermal expansion. This is one of the main reasons why MS is preferred over copper (16×10^{-6} per deg. C.) and Aluminum ($23 \times 10^{-6} \text{ deg.}^{-1} \text{ C.}^{-1}$). Bond strength can be ensured during thermal expansion with an equal thermal coefficient, preventing bond failure [11]. The frame and the shaft are made of mild steel which are better than Aluminum and Titanium in terms of stiffness, strength, and weight. Aluminum, chromium, copper, and nickel are all added to alloy steels such as AISI 4140. The pulleys were made of an aluminum casting alloy that has a number of benefits which helped to maintain the shaft speed due to light weight. The properties of aluminum alloy include high fluidity, low melting point, short casting times, low hot cracking propensity, strong as-cast surface finish, and chemical stability [12]. A tabular list of selected design materials is shown in Table 3.3.

Table 3.3: Selected Materials of the Machine

Designed Components	Selected Materials
Frame	Cast Iron
Connecting Shaft	Mild Steel
Belt Drive	Leather
Driven Pulley	Mild Steel
Bevel Pinion	Mild Steel
Disc	Mild Steel

3.4 Components of the Machine

(a) AC Motor

An AC motor is an electric motor driven by an alternating current. The AC motor commonly consists of two basic parts, an outside stator having coils supplied with alternating current to produce a rotating magnetic field, and an inside rotor attached to the output shaft producing a second rotating field. The rotor magnetic field may be produced by permanent magnets or DC or AC electrical windings [13]. The AC motor that had been used in this paper is of 1HP=746 watt. Voltage and maximum rotation of the AC motor are 220V and 1420 rpm.

Fig 3.4(b): AC motor**(b) Shaft**

A shaft is a circular rotating machine element that transfers power from one component to another or from a power-producing machine to a power-absorbing machine. For conventional shafts, mild steel is the preferred material. When high strength is required, an alloy steel such as nickel, nickel-chromium, or chromium-vanadium steel is employed. Hot rolling is used to shape shafts, which are subsequently cold drawn or turned and ground to scale [14]. In figure 3.4(b) has shown a mild steel shaft. In the paper there were used 3 shafts for transmitting power from the AC motor to rotate different shafts.

Fig 3.4(c): Mild Steel Shaft [14].**(c) V-Belt**

A v-belt is a flexible machine element used to transmit power between a set of grooved pulleys or sheaves. They are mainly characterized as belts having a trapezium cross-section. V-belts are the most widely used belts drives since their geometry causes them to wedge tightly into the groove as the tension is increased. During an operation, the friction causes the belt to grip onto the pulley. The rotation of the driver pulley increases the tension on one side of the belt creating a tight side [15]. Here in this paper, three v-belt were used such as B-53 inch, B-40 inch, B-35 inch etc.

Fig 3.4(d): V-Belt**(d) Bearing**

Bearings are components that help objects rotate. They protect the rotating shaft inside the machinery from damage. Automobiles, airplanes, electric motors, and other machines use bearings [16]. Total six number of bearings are required. Two of them were required for front shaft. Another two were required for middle shaft. And the last two were for joining the shaft 3. All of the bearings are ball bearing type. Fig. 3.4(d) shows different bearing used.

Fig 3.4(e): Ball Bearing [16]

(e) Pulley

A pulley is a wheel that carries a flexible rope, cord, cable, chain, or belt in its rim. Pulleys are used singly or in combination to transmit energy and motion. In belt drive, pulleys are affixed to shafts at their axes, and power is transmitted between the shafts by means of endless belts running over the pulleys. There were used two double pulleys and three single pulleys mounted on the shafts for constructing the machine. In fig 3.4(e) pulleys are shown.

Fig 3.4(f): Pulleys**(f) Hacksaw Blade**

A hacksaw is full of a fine-toothed blade under tension in a frame, used for cutting metal. Hand-held hacksaws consist of a metal frame with a handle, and pins for attaching a narrow disposable blade. The blade is put under tension via a screw. The high-speed steel blades are perfect for cutting hard materials such as steel. A hacksaw blade of (12 inch length) was used here for cutting mild steel. Figure 3.4(f) has shown us the hacksaw blade that was used.

Fig 3.4(g): Hacksaw Blade**(g) Drill chuck and drill tool**

The devices which are used to hold a drill or other cutting tools on a spindle are known as drill chucks. Basically, for a simple drilling operation a keyed chuck is used through which a drill bit can tighten or loosen. Drill bits or drills are cutting tools used to remove material to create holes. Drills come in many sizes and shapes. The drill chuck that was used to perform drilling operation can hold (1.5mm – 13mm) drill bit shown in figure 3.4(g).

Fig 3.4(h): Drill chuck and drill tool**(h) Blade cutting tool**

A blade is a type of stone tool created by striking a long narrow flake from a stone core. A rotary blade cutter is used for fast cuts. A blade cutting tool of 4 inch diameter was used to perform cutting operation in the constructed machine. In figure 3.4(h) the cutting blade has shown.

Fig 3.4(i): Blade cutting tool

3.5 Specifications of Machine Components: (Table 3.5)

Components	Specification of the Components
Frame	Length=34 inch=86.36cm Width=20 inch=50.8cm Height=30 inch=76.2cm
Bevel-pinion	No. of teeth(T_1)=11(power transmission) No. of teeth(T_2)=16(drill tool) Pitch cone angle=45 degree
Shaft	No. of Shaft=3 Length of Shaft 1, L_1 = 28 inch=71.12cm Length of Shaft 2, L_2 =27 inch=68.58cm Length of Shaft 3, L_3 =13 inch=33.02cm Diameter of shaft, D = 1 inch=2.54cm Distance between Shaft 1 and 2= distance between shaft 2 and 3= 9.5 inch=24.13cm
V-Belt	No. of belt=3 Length of belt 1, L_1 = 53 inch=134.62cm Length of belt 2, L_2 = 40 inch=101.6cm Length of belt 3, L_3 = 35 inch=88.9cm
Pulley	Number of pulleys= 5 Diameter of Pulley 1, D_1 = 3 inch=7.62cm Diameter of pulley 2, D_2 = 10 inch=25.4cm Diameter of pulley 3, D_3 = 3 inch=7.62cm Diameter of double pulley 4, D_4 = 9 inch (large)=22.86cm D_4 = 7 inch (small)=17.78cm Diameter of pulley 5, D_5 = 2.5 inch=6.35cm
Cutting Blade	Diameter of cutting blade= 4 inch=10.16cm
Grinding Wheel	Diameter of grinding wheel= 4 inch=10.16cm
Components	Specification of the Components
Buffing Wheel	Diameter of buffing wheel= 4 inch=10.16cm
Motor	AC motor, 220 V, Power = 1hp

3.6 Design Calculation

CALCULATION OF SPEED OF MAIN SHAFT

Since, motor and main shaft connected through belt pulley mechanism. The speed of main shaft had been calculated. From the relation of speed and diameter equation (1.1) can be defined as,

$$N_s/N_m = D_a/D_b \quad (1.1)$$

Where, N_s is the speed of the main shaft, N_m is the speed of the motor which is 1420 rpm, D_a is the diameter of the motor pulley which is 76.2 mm, D_b is the diameter of the main shaft pulley which is 254 mm.

So, the speed of the main shaft is given under equation (1.2).

$$N_s = (D_a/D_b) * N_m \quad (1.2)$$

$$N_s = (76.2/254) * 1420$$

$N_s = 426$ rpm Therefore, main shaft speed is 426 rpm.

CALCULATION OF SPEED OF SECOND SHAFT

Since, second shaft and main shaft connected through belt pulley mechanism. I calculated the speed of second shaft. From the relation of speed and diameter equation (2.1) can be defined as, $N_y/N_s = D_c/D_d$ (2.1)

Where, N_y is the speed of the second shaft, N_s is the speed of the main shaft which is 426 rpm, D_c is the diameter of the main shaft pulley which is 76.2mm and D_d is the diameter of the second shaft pulley which is 228.26 mm. So, the speed of the second shaft is given under equation (2.2).

$$N_y = (D_c/D_d) * N_s \quad (2.2)$$

$$N_y = (76.2/228.26) * 426$$

$N_y = 142$ rpm Therefore, second shaft speed is 142rpm.

CALCULATION OF HACKSAW CUTTING SPEED

$$\text{Angular velocity} = \omega * r \quad (2.3)$$

Where, r is the radius of the crank wheel which is $\omega = 4.72 \text{ inch} = 12 \text{ cm} = 0.12 \text{ m}$. Angular speed can be,

$$\text{Angular speed } (\omega) = 2\pi N/60 \text{ rad/sec} \quad (2.4)$$

Where, N is the speed of crank wheel in rpm which is 142rpm.

Therefore, from equations (2.3) and (2.4),

$$\omega = 2 * \pi * 142/60 = 14.87 \text{ rad/sec}$$

$$V = 14.87 * 0.12 = 1.784 \text{ m/sec}$$

$$V = 1.784 * 60 = 107.064 \text{ m/min.}$$

Therefore, the angular velocity of hacksaw is 107.064 m/min.

CALCULATION OF DRILLING SPEED

No. of teeth on gear to be 16 and no. of teeth on pinion to be 11. This is done by the relation given under equation (2.5),

$$N_d/N_y = (16/11) \quad (2.5)$$

$$N_d = (16/11) * N_y$$

$$N_d = (16/11) * 142$$

$$N_d = 206.54 \text{ rpm}$$

This equation gives the value of the drilling speed as stated below. $N_d = 206.54$ rpm.

CALCULATION OF GRINDING SPEED AND BLADE CUTTING SPEED

Since, grinder wheel assembled on main shaft. So, the speed of grinder wheel will be same as speed of main shaft. Therefore, the speed of grinder wheel equals to 426 rpm. Similarly, the speed of the cutting blade equals to 426 rpm as it is assembled on the main shaft too.

CALCULATION OF SPEED OF THIRD SHAFT

Since second shaft and third shaft connected through belt pulley mechanism. I calculated the speed of main shaft. From the relation of speed and diameter equation (2.1) can be defined as,

$$N_k/N_y = D_k / D_c \quad (2.1)$$

Where, N_k is the speed of the second shaft, N_y is the speed of the second shaft which is 142 rpm, D_k is the diameter of the third shaft pulley which is 63.5 mm and D_c is the diameter of the second shaft pulley which is 177.8 mm. So, the speed of the third shaft is given under equation (2.2).

$$N_k = (D_k / D_c) * N_y \quad (2.2)$$

$$N_k = (63.5 / 177.8) * 142$$

$$N_k = 50.71 \text{ rpm}$$

Therefore, third shaft speed is 50.71rpm.

CALCULATION OF SPEED OF BUFFING AND PRESSURE CUTTING

Since, buffing wheel assembled on third shaft. So, the speed of buffing wheel will be same as speed of third shaft. Therefore, the speed of grinder wheel equals to 50.71 rpm. Similarly, the speed of the pressure cutting equals to 50.71 rpm as it is assembled on the main shaft too.

3.7 Construction Procedure

For constructing the Multi-Purpose Mechanical Cutting Machine, a frame was constructed firstly. The frame was rectangle in shape and was made of mild steel (length 34 inch, width 20 inch, height 30 inch). Six Operations were mounted on the frame such as drilling, grinding, hacksaw cutting, blade cutting, buffing and pressure cutting. Then the three shafts were jointed on the frame with 6 UC bearings (no 205) and 12 pairs of nut and bolts. Fives pulleys were used in this paper. Different sizes of pulley were used to manage the shaft speed. After that four pulleys were arranged on the different three shafts parallel with the main shaft. Three V-Belt were used to transmit the power to different shafts. First belt was connected between pulley 1(P1) and 2 (P2) to rotate the main shaft which was mounted on the top right side of the frame. The second belt was connected between pulley 3 (P3) and 4 (P4) to rotate the second shaft which was mounted at the middle of the frame. Again, the third belt was connected between pulley 4 (P4) and 5 (P5) which was mounted at the left side of the frame. After finishing the belt pulley arrangement, a cutting blade and a grinding wheel were attached to the opposite end of the main shaft to perform blade cutting and grinding operation. Then the Crank Slider Mechanism was applied by attaching a crank connected with a hacksaw blade at one end of the second shaft. A bevel-pinion was also arranged at the other end of the shaft to rotate the drill chuck including drill bit (1.5mm-13mm). After all, the buffing wheel was attached at one end of the third shaft and an arrangement of pressure cutting operation using crank slider mechanism was also attached at the other end of that shaft. Finally, an AC motor (220v, 1420 rpm) was connected through pulley 1 (P1) to rotate the main shaft to operate the whole operations.

3.8 Actual model of Multi-Purpose Mechanical machine

All the procedures were completed carefully. Proposed “Multi-Purpose Mechanical Cutting Machine” was constructed according to the proposed design. After construction and several modifications, the final constructed model is shown in Fig. 3.8(a)

Fig 3.8(a): Top side view

Fig 3.8(b): Right side view

Fig 3.8(c): Front side view

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Performance Test and Data Acquisition

Performance test of the constructed Multi-Purpose Mechanical Cutting Machine was done on various and different sizes of metal. Different types of thickness were taken of mild steel to test the performance. All the metals were mild steel.

Material-1 (Thickness = 4mm, width = 19mm)

Table 4.1(a): Time analysis on the basis of material-1

Operations	Manual	Multi-purpose machine
Blade cutting	5 sec	11 sec
Drilling	9.5 sec	15 sec
Hacksaw cutting	2 min	1 min 20 sec
	Total time = 2.24 min	Total time = 1.76 min

$$\text{Time}_{\text{manual}} / \text{Time}_{\text{machine}} = 2.24 / 1.76$$

$$= 1.27$$

Time required manually is 1.27 times the time required by operation in multi-purpose machine for this performance test.

Material-2 (Thickness = 2mm, width = 20mm)

Table 4.1(b): Time analysis on the basis of material-2

Operations	Manual	Multi-purpose machine
Blade cutting	4 sec	6 sec
Drilling	4.50 sec	10 sec
Hacksaw cutting	1 min 30 sec	50 sec
	Total time = 1.64 min	Total time = 1.1 min

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Time}_{\text{manual}} / \text{Time}_{\text{machine}} &= 1.64 / 1.1 \\ &= 1.49 \end{aligned}$$

Time required manually is 1.49 times the time required by operation in multi-purpose mechanical machine for this performance test.

Material-3 (Thickness = 1.5mm)

Table 4.1(c): Time analysis on the basis of material-3

Operations	Manual	Multi-purpose machine
Pressure cutting	2 sec	1 sec

Material-4 (Thickness =2 mm)

Table 4.1(d): Time analysis on the basis of material-4

Operations	Manual	Multi-purpose machine
Pressure cutting	3 sec	2 sec

Hacksaw Cutting

Table 4.1(e): Time analysis on the basis of material

Material	Manual	Multi-purpose machine
Thickness = 12mm	3 min 10 sec	2 min 20 sec
Thickness = 4mm	2 min	1 min 20 sec
Thickness = 2mm	1 min 30 sec	50 sec

Performance test of Grinding and Buffing

All the materials that had been tested to measure the performance can be easily surface finished by grinding wheel of any thickness. Polishing was done by buffing tool of different materials of different thickness.

Test analysis of Hacksawing, Drilling, Blade cutting and Pressure cutting

The performance test of the hacksaw cutting was done quite smoothly. During this operation, the high speed hacksaw blade was in proper direction to cut the metal. The metals of 12mm, 4mm and 2mm thickness were cut properly by the hacksaw blade.

Again, the performance test of drilling was done on various materials of different thickness. During the operation, the force was created by hand on the upward direction to drill the metal. To perform the operation maximum force should be placed on the materials to drill it quickly.

The performance test of the blade cutting operation was done properly. It was quite tough to cut any rough surfaces with the single cutting blade. The cutting tool had been used to cut any plain steel sheet preciously. Also, the pressure cutting was performed correctly with a crank slider mechanism.

4.2 Results

The results are obtained from the performance tests of different materials. In the tests, it is shown that the speed of the manual machine is higher than the multi-purpose machine. The power consumption is required also high for an individual machine comparison with a multi-purpose machine. In the performance test for material 1, the time measurement for blade cutting, drilling and hacksaw cutting were 5 sec, 9.5 sec and 2 min respectively of a manual machine while times were 11 sec, 15 sec and 1 min 20 sec for multi-purpose machine to perform the same operations. It shows that time required manually is 1.27 times the time required by operation in multi-purpose machine for these performance test. Similarly for the second test for material 2 that time required manually is 1.49 times the time required by operation in multi-purpose machine.

For the performance test of pressure cutting, two materials were taken with different thickness of 1.5 mm and 2 mm respectively. Times for both metals were quite same.

Again, for the performance test of hacksaw cutting, three materials were taken with thickness of 12 mm, 4 mm and 2 mm respectively. Here times required for manual operations were 1-2 min more than the times required

to perform in multi-purpose machine. However, the surfaced finishing and the polishing operations were carefully done by the grinding and buffing tool.

Table 4.2 (a): Results analysis based on performance tests and other aspects.

Sr No.	Parameter	Manual machine	Multi-purpose machine
1	Speed	Speed is high	Speed is low
2	Power consumption	High	Low
3	Machining cost	High	Low
4	Time for all operation	(1.27 to 1.49 times) more than MPM	Less
5	Labor cost	More	Less
6	Space required	More	Less

4.3 Discussion

The multi-purpose mechanical cutting machine was designed to perform various operations at a time with a single motor. According to design all the necessary parts were assembled. The structure of the machine had been designed considering all the important safety factors. There were some theoretical values that had been collected from the parts of the design dimension. A number of material tests were taken to measure the performance. As it is a multi-functional machine, it reduces the cost for the individual device. Operating this type of machine is very easy and any one can run this machine easily. Operations like hacksaw cutting, single blade cutting, drilling, grinding, pressure cutting and buffing were performed more properly.

Hacksaw cutting operation performed in this machine was quite faster than the manually operated machine. The operation was done using the crank slider mechanism which provided a continuous speed to the hacksaw blade. Different sizes of metal could be cut by this blade. Again, the single cutting blade was used to perform blade cutting operation which was done more accurately comparison with an individual cutter machine. There was a drilling portion in which the drilling operation was performed on various materials of different thickness. This precision and the accuracy of this operation was as far as similar to individual drilling machine. A crank slider mechanism was also used in the portion of pressure cutting which was done properly.

However, the surfaced finishing and the polishing operations were carefully done by the grinding and buffing tool. Use of simple shaft has helped us to reduce the vibration of the complete device of its half. All the measurement of time, speed and depth of cutting operations in this machine were calculated very carefully and preciously. After all the observations and the performance tests it is shown that the time, manufacturing cost and power consumptions are reduced in a multi-purpose machine. A less floor area is required in this machine comparison to manual machine. So, a multi-purpose machine is quite preferable for multi tasks operations in industries than a manually operated machine.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a machine is designed which is capable of performing operations such as drilling, blade cutting, hacksaw cutting, pressure cutting, grinding and buffing at different working centers simultaneously which implies that industrialist have not to pay for machine performing above tasks individually for operating operation simultaneously. The main purpose of this paper is to perform six different operations at a time in a single machine to reduce workload, space, time, and manufacturing cost. This multi-purpose machine has fulfilled all the objectives and purposes that was aimed. This single multi-purpose cutting machine is quite preferable than any conventional machine in all these aspects. As all the operations can be performed at one place. This machine can be used as part of remote places where energy is inadequate or sporadic.

The following conclusions can also be drawn as follows:

- The design of the machine is relatively simple.
- The machine is useful particularly for small scale industries.
- Number of operations can be carried out on the single machine.

- Power consumptions is reduced.
- Small floor area is required.
- Workers movements can be minimized by utilizing multiple operations at one setup.
- Manufacturing and maintenance costs can be reduced.
- This process is fully mechanical without using much of electronics.

In near future, this type of lightweight and potable machine will be implemented in every small and large scale industries with automation process. This type of machine can easily be used by anyone due to its simplicity of working and doing wide range of operations. Even unskilled work can deal with it effectively and, in light of this, the cost of creation can be minimized which is the most important factor in the industry.

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS

Further research can be done on the multi-purpose mechanical cutting machine are,

- Other operations can be incorporated in to the machine.
- Shaping operation can be performed by introducing a shaping tool at the counter shaft.
- Boring operation can be performed by introducing a boring tool by replacing drilling.
- The speed of motor can be changed by attaching a gearbox.
- The machine can be made more portable.

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